

In vivo recording of visually evoked potentials with novel full diamond ECoG implants

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Thin film technology
Neural implants
Boron-doped diamond
Microfabrication
Microelectrodes
Brain-computer interface
Visually evoked potential
CVD diamond

ABSTRACT

Implantable neuroprosthetic devices such as electrocorticography (ECoG) and intracortical microelectrodes have the potential to restore neurological functions in disabled individuals. They constitute the direct interface with the body and require long term efficiency. We propose an ultra-thin diamond-based implant to tackle challenges related with long term implantation, and demonstrate its functionality on rodents. Here we take advantage of thin-film diamond to generate not only the electrodes but also the thin passivation foil, leading to a full thin film diamond ECoG. Implants were fabricated based on boron-doped diamond (BDD) electrodes connected through titanium nitride (TiN) conductive tracks, all being encapsulated in intrinsic diamond. A complete electrochemical characterization proved that the TiN tracks were well embedded inside diamond and the efficiency of the BDD electrodes. Functionality of the ECoG device was also provided by the recording of classic visual evoked potentials (VEPs) on wild-type mice and rats. This thin film diamond technology successfully responds to long term issues (linked with electrode material or device packaging) and holds the potential to inspire and pave the way for future generations of various electrode arrays.

1. Introduction

Wearable neuroprosthetic devices offer the promise of restoring neurological functions for disabled individuals. For instance, recent developments in the field of brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) implanted in the central nervous system demonstrated the possibility of controlling prosthetic limbs through electrocorticography (ECoG) recordings of the brain activity [4,17]. Electrical stimulation through penetrating microelectrodes also enabled the recovery of some visual perceptions [16]. Despite encouraging results [2,51], chronic intracortical or subdural implants are still not available on the market due to several issues linked to the electrode material or the device packaging. Electrode efficiency can for instance be limited by the tissue responses or gliosis at the interface to the foreign and rigid device [22,39]. Indeed, the reaction is

likely to be promoted by the mechanical mismatch between the electrode material and the neural tissue. Besides the host body responses, repetitive electrical stimulation can lead to dissolution of the metallic electrode layers [9]. Failure can also occur at the level of a subsequent polymer coating: delamination and peeling of the passivation layer have been frequently reported in literature [12,30,44]. During the clinical study for the Retina Implant AG subretinal prosthesis for example, migration of water during months after post-implantation has also demonstrated it can induce electromigration of the embedded metal, which progressively degraded the performance of the implant [13]. To solve these issues and to create water-tight structures, several research teams have proposed innovative approaches such as stacked layers of inorganic and organic materials [1].

Implants fabricated by conventional technology are usually based of

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.diamond.2024.111335>

Received 9 November 2023; Received in revised form 1 June 2024; Accepted 22 June 2024

Available online 24 June 2024

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metal tracks with electrodes embedded in a biocompatible polymer insulation layer. Recent advances in the field of material bioengineering showed that the immune response of tissues can be reduced by selecting biocompatible and soft materials which are required to follow the cortical tissue topology [8,21]. Among the novel materials being investigated, diamond is a carbon-based material which has received consequent attention in the neuro-engineering field, and that demonstrated high stability of the covalent bonds between carbon atoms confers both structural stability and chemical inertness [28]. As it is hermetic to small molecules like water, its use as an encapsulation material should reduce thereby the risk of implant swelling [18,35].

Intrinsic diamond is also an electrical insulator, while doped diamond possesses attractive electrochemical properties for neural interfacing due to its semi-conductor properties. Ultra-nanocrystalline diamond with nitrogen inclusion (N-UNCD) grown in polycrystalline diamond substrate mills were introduced in diamond-based subretinal implants [23,42], but such chips remained thick (100 to 250 μm), and were embedded into polymer, limiting the global flexibility to conformally follow the tissues. Nonetheless, the nitrogen-doped-diamond-based implants demonstrated some promising recording functionality. [50]. Similarly, Boron-doped diamond (BDD) electrodes feature excellent electrochemical characteristics with a large potential window (3 V) in aqueous media [38]. Such material stability is highly desirable for neural stimulation. With the evolution of diamond production technologies, very thin diamond layers of a few hundred nanometers in its nanocrystalline form can now be engineered using specific plasma CVD reactors [20]. Manufactured BDD electrodes have been used for neural recordings [27,38] as well as for neurotransmitters sensing [15]. In parallel, the biocompatibility of both CVD diamond N-UNCD electrodes and BDD electrodes was successfully demonstrated on a broad range of neural cells and tissues both *in vitro* and *in vivo* [5,6,41,45,46].

Convinced that diamond in its intrinsic or doped form represents the material of choice to manufacture long-term biocompatible and hermetic neural interfaces, we have developed using conventional nanotechnology approaches, a process flow for the fabrication of a full-diamond-based electrocorticography electrode array, and assessed its characteristics and functionality for recording purposes. The major achievement relies on the design and fabrication of the nanocrystalline BDD electrodes embedded in an intrinsic ultra-thin diamond matrix. The resulting thin and flexible full-diamond ECoG implant is, to our knowledge, the first that combines BDD electrodes in an intrinsic diamond flexible structure. Although hermetic full diamond feedthrough arrays with UNCD electrodes had been investigated by Bionic Vision Australia, we have here developed a complete novel process better compatible with standard micro-technological processes and resulting into a fully flexible thin implant. Another diamond electrode has been published [3] with a needle-shape geometry showing a tip in BDD and undoped diamond as coating on a standard tungsten needle. Our work proposes a totally different planar geometry solution with a flexible solution compatible with the ECoG constraints of mapping the brain surface in a way as conformal as possible.

2. Materials and methods

A. Intrinsic and boron-doped diamond growth process

Nanocrystalline diamond coatings were grown on 4-in. wafers using microwave assisted plasma chemical vapour deposition (MPCVD) in a SEKI SDS6K reactor with hydrogen plasma containing methane as the source of carbon [34]. Trimethylboron (TMB) was added to the gas phase for doping in the case of BDD electrode preparation. The boron concentration in the crystal was in the range of 2.10^{21} at.cm³. Diamond films were grown over 4in substrates at a typical pressure of 30 Torr and powers of 3000 W. The substrate temperature was kept low, between 650 °C and 780 °C and the growth durations were respectively of 4.5 h and 12 h for intrinsic diamond and BDD coatings. Prior to growth, the

substrates were seeded according to a process we described in the literature [20], using 5-nm-negatively-charged Detonation Nano-diamond Suspensions in de-ionised (DI) water (1 wt%) from Adámas.

Diamond grown layers deposited on 4 in. substrates were patterned either (i) using reactive-ion etching (RIE) in a mixture of O₂/CF₄ plasmas (so called “top-down” below) or by (ii) alternatively using a selective growth approach after preparation of a seeding nucleation layer, this layer was coated with a protective coating that was patterned using conventional lithography: exposure to plasma enabled to remove the nucleation layer in non-protected areas, thus confining the diamond growth to these regions while being prevented in other regions (“bottom-up” below). During the whole process described below, we switched between these two methods depending on the diamond layer (intrinsic or boron doped) and the fabrication needs.

B. Full-diamond implant microfabrication

The entire process was developed on standard 550 μm -thick Silicon substrates with a 1.5 μm -thick thermal SiO₂ layer. The wafer was pre-activated in Ar/O₂ plasma (with pressure 110 mTorr, power 90 W, flow rates 50 sccm O₂ and 40 sccm Ar, during 5 min) prior to diamond nanoparticle electrostatic seeding. After the seeding step, the wafer was then placed inside the MPCVD reactor in order to grow the diamond seeds slightly for a few minutes to obtain a good adhesion of the nanoparticles over the whole surface of the wafer.

To restrict the diamond growth to a specific pattern, localised growth was carried out as follows. After the initial diamond nanoparticle seeding (step 1 in Fig. 1(A)), a thin layer of aluminium nitride (AlN: yellow in Fig. 1(A)) was sputtered over the diamond nanoparticles (MP500S, PLASSYS) under the following conditions: pressure $0.53 \cdot 10^{-2}$ mbar, power 500 W, flow rates 14 sccm for Ar and 27 sccm for N₂, and deposition time 30 min. AlN, which can withstand plasma conditions in the diamond growth reactor, was used here as a masking layer during the growth of non-doped diamond (C* light blue in Fig. 1(A)). The AlN layer was then patterned by photolithography and wet etched in order to open the areas where diamond had to grow (step 2 in Fig. 1(A)). The wafer was then introduced inside the chamber of the SEKI diamond reactor (3000 W, 30 Torr, 500 sccm H₂ and 7.5 sccm CH₄, during 4 h30). These conditions resulted in a 1 μm -thick intrinsic diamond film measured by a mechanical profilometer (Dektak XT, Bruker). The AlN mask was then removed using an alkaline etchant (photoresist developer PRD 238, CMC Materials) (step 3 in Fig. 1(A)).

The next step consisted in growing a BDD layer directly on the whole substrate, to obtain the conductive parts of the implants. The wafer was again seeded with diamond nanoparticles and then introduced in another SEKI diamond reactor dedicated to doping, with TMB added in the gas mixture to grow a 600-nm-thick BDD layer, under the reported growth conditions [24]. At this stage, the wafer was completely covered with the BDD layer. The patterning of BDD tracks and electrodes was achieved through the top-down approach, by depositing an aluminium nitride (AlN) masking layer of 500 nm patterned by photolithography and etching the unwanted BDD in a RIE equipment (NE110, Nextral) with the following parameters: power 100 W, pressure 37.5 mTorr, flow rates 40.6 sccm O₂, 2.2 sccm CF₄, during 900 s. After this localised BDD etching, the remaining Al masking layer was completely removed in the AlN chemical etchant bath (TechniEtch Al80, TECHNIC) (step 5 in Fig. 1(A)).

As the resistivity of BDD is too high ($> 10^{-2}$ Ohm.cm) to be used alone as conductive material under the electrode pads and over the tracks, additional conductive tracks were produced to decrease the serial resistance of the implant alongside its foil. Titanium nitride (TiN) was used to guarantee stability and compatibility under the harsh conditions of diamond growth, especially the high temperatures around 600 °C inside the reactor, as previously reported [36]. TiN deposition was carried out with the following parameters in the sputtering equipment: a pressure controlled at $0.5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ mbar, a power of 150 W, balanced gas

Fig. 1. Design and microfabrication of the full diamond ECoG. (A) Description of the fabrication steps for a full diamond implant. PDDAC for Polycationic polymers, such as poly(diallyldimethylammonium) chloride. Si = Silicon, SiO₂ = Silicon Dioxide, AlN = Aluminium nitride, NPs = Nanoparticles, C* = intrinsic diamond, BDD = Boron-Doped Diamond, TiN = Titanium Nitride, DRIE = Deep Reactive Ion Etching. (B) Cross-section schematic view of the implant; (C) schematic drawing of the implant –top view.

flow rates of 20 sccm Ar and 20 sccm N₂. TiN tracks were defined using standard photolithography, then etched in hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), creating an annular contact around the BDD electrode along with tracks and pads (TiN: brown, step 6 in Fig. 1(A)). To finalise our full-diamond implants, a second layer of intrinsic diamond was seeded to encapsulate the conductive layer (step 7 in Fig. 1(A)). Here, the etching process could not be used to open the diamond layer because there is low selectivity between BDD and intrinsic diamond layers. We used another AlN mask to protect the electrodes and the contact pads during the diamond growth (step 8 in Fig. 1(A)). At this stage, the result is a fully hermetic diamond structure with individual TiN tracks embedded inside a

protective non-doped diamond layer whereas opened BDD electrodes (step 9 in Fig. 1(A)) are made available as electrochemical probes. The SEM image (Neon 40, Carl Zeiss) shows the finished electrode diamond structure (Fig. 2(B)).

The diamond implant was finally embedded in parylene (pink in Fig. 1(A)) to ease its manipulation by the veterinary surgeon (from 1.5 μm with diamond only to 15 μm thickness with additional parylene packaging). Note that it could be replaced by biodegradable polymer in the future. A 7 μm-thick film was deposited on the top side of the wafer to obtain the first polymer encapsulating layer. A thin layer of Al was then deposited to protect the parylene film. Lithography was performed

Fig. 2. Fabricated implants. (A) Photography of an implant at the end of the process after laser cutting, (B) Scanning electron microscope (SEM) image of fabricated Boron-Doped Diamond (BDD) electrodes composed of a Titanium nitride (TiN) track on top connected via an annular contact – the whole being packaged inside intrinsic diamond (C*) layers. Scale bar represents 200 μm. (C) Magnification view of a 400-μm-diameter BDD electrode and C* packaging with TiN layer underneath (Neon 40, Carl Zeiss).

to open the parylene layer locally on the electrodes and contact pads (step 10 in Fig. 1(A)). The openings of these contact pads and electrodes were made with dry-etching using O_2/CF_4 plasma (conditions of the plasma: pressure 125 mTorr, power 100 W, O_2 50 sccm, CF_4 10 sccm). The wafer was then cleaned and 500 nm of Al layer was deposited on its back side. A back-side lithography step was performed to localise openings in the Al layer below the implant. Next, the SiO_2 layer was dry-etched and the silicon was etched by Deep Reactive Ion Etching (DRIE) (A160E, ALCATEL) (Step 11 in Fig. 1(A)).

In practice, a piece of silicon wafer underneath the contact pads area was kept during the final steps of the process for better handling purposes and to support good mechanical stability for the electrical contact. Subsequently, the SiO_2 layer under the implant was removed in buffered HF solution. Hence, the second 7 μm -thick parylene layer was deposited on the backside of the implants (Step 12 in Fig. 1(A)).

Finally, the implants were ready to be released from the wafer after LASER ablation (UP-213, New Wave Research). Each 4 in. wafer was enabling the patterned production of typically 30 individual full diamond implants. The step of LASER cutting was required to optimize the number of implants per wafer, allowing a circular positioning of the implants on the wafer instead of classical columns/rows repartition.

C. Assembly of the implants

A connector was soldered to a specific PCB board (RS) which was mounted on the implants. The welding was performed using a stencil to spread the conductive paste over the pieces to be soldered. Then, a pick-and-place machine (Tresky AG) was used to join the pieces and the implant together. Finally, the mounted devices were put inside an oven at 150 °C for 5 min so that the conductive paste could seize. The resulting assembly was stiffened with UV glue to ensure its robustness. The piece of Si wafer left from the process reinforces the connection between the contact pads and the PCB board.

D. Electrode characterization

Before *in vivo* experiments, the electrochemical characteristics of the implants were measured by standard electrochemical techniques. Cyclic Voltammetry (CV) and Electro-chemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) were performed using a SP-200 potentiostat from Biologic, interfaced by the EC-lab Express software. The 3-electrode electrochemical cell was composed of the tested BDD electrodes (surface area: 0.031, 0.126 or 0.283 cm^2) as the working electrode, a platinum wire as the counter electrode, and an Ag/AgCl pellet as the reference electrode. Each electrode was cycled 3 times between -1.5 to 1.5 V at a sweep rate of 100 $\text{mV}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. EIS was carried out in a 0.01 M Phosphate-Buffered Saline (PBS) solution (Sigma-Aldrich). The signal was swept across the system at frequencies ranging from 1 MHz to 1 Hz. CV was performed in the presence of 0.5 M lithium perchlorate (LiClO_4 , Sigma-Aldrich), a conductive electrolyte.

E. Animal surgery

Visually evoked potentials were recorded on rodents in two laboratories. Adult ($n = 2$, age > 1-month-old) C57BL/6 J mice (Charles River Laboratories) were used at Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne – EPFL (Lausanne, Switzerland) and Long Evans rats ($n = 2$, age = 26.5 weeks old, Janvier Labs) at the Vision Institute (IDV, Paris, France). At EPFL in Switzerland, experiments were conducted according to the animal authorisation GE/193/19 approved by the Département de l'emploi, des affaires sociales et de la santé (DEAS), Direction générale de la santé de la République et Canton de Genève. At IDV in France, the experiments and procedures were both approved by the Local Animal Ethics Committee N°005 (registration number APAFIS #15258–2,018,052,811,521,506 v1). The rodents were kept in a 12 h day/night cycle with access to food and water *ad libitum*. White light

(300 \pm 50 lx) was on from 8 a.m. to 8 p.m. at IDV (with no light during the night) and from 7 a.m. to 7 p.m. at EPFL, with red light (650–720 nm, 80–100 lx) during the night.

At EPFL, the mice were all anesthetized by intraperitoneal injection of ketamine (87.5 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) and xylazine (12.5 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$). Analgesia was performed by subcutaneous injection of buprenorphine (0.1 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) and lidocaine (6 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$). Artificial tears were used to prevent the eyes from drying. The depth of anesthesia was assessed with the pedal reflex. The skin of the head was shaved and cleaned with betadine. Mice were placed on a stereotaxic frame, and the skin was opened to expose the skull. A craniotomy was performed to expose the visual cortex. At IDV, the rats were anesthetized with an intraperitoneal injection of ketamine (40 mg/Kg , Axience, France) and medetomidine (0.14 mg/kg , Domitor®, Vétquinol, France) diluted in sodium chloride. Buprenorphine (0.05 mg/kg , Buprecare®, Med'Vet, France) and Dexamethasone solution (Dexazone®, Virbac, France) were injected subcutaneously to reduce any inflammation and pain. After being shaved, a local analgesic, Lidocaine (4 mg/kg , Laocaine, MSD, France) was administered subcutaneously under the scalp skin and Xylocaine gel (2 %) was applied in the ears. A surgical craniotomy was also performed under anesthesia, after disinfection with iodopovidone solution and a sagittal incision revealing the skull.

The remaining periosteum was removed and the skull was cleaned with H_2O_2 . A rectangular piece of bone was removed in the presence of cortex buffer by drilling with 0.07- and 0.05-mm diameter drill bits, revealing the visual cortex. In both cases, the temperature of the animals was maintained at 37 °C with a heating pad.

F. Visually Evoked Potentials (VEPs) recordings

In both cases, Visually-evoked potentials (VEPs) were recorded in a dark room at ambient temperature. Our diamond implant was placed in contact with the dura and tested with different set-ups.

At EPFL, a Ganzfeld light stimulator was used to send light flashes (20 ms, 1 Hz, repeated 20 times). Signals were pre-amplified (Biomedica Mangoni, BM 623 HC4) and band-passed on-line between 0.1 and 200 Hz. Data was acquired at a frequency of 1.0 kHz. Visual acuity tests were also performed on the anesthetized normal adult mice. A custom Matlab program was used to control chessboard patterns on a screen 50 cm apart from the eyes of the mice. Visual acuities under 0.1, 0.2, and 0.3 cycles per degrees conditions repeated 30 times were assessed while brain signals were recorded using the same pre-amplifier. VEPs data were analysed on Matlab. Raw data were first filtered with a Butterworth second order filter, to remove electromagnetic interferences at 50 Hz, and then band passed between 1 and 100 Hz. Signals from the electrodes were averaged in alignment with the trigger onset provided by the Ganzfeld stimulator. Mean amplitudes and latencies were calculated. Results are expressed in terms of mean \pm error of the mean. Comparison between mean peak-to-peak amplitude was achieved by one-way ANOVA with Dunn-Sidak multi-comparison correction tests. *P*-values are symbolised as follows: **p* < 0.05, ***p* < 0.01, ****p* < 0.001. Signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) was calculated as the ratio between P1-N1 peak-to-peak amplitude and twice the root mean square of the baseline taken as 90 ms before the light onset.

At IDV, a collimated white LED (MWWHL1, ThorLabs, USA) controlled by a stimulus generator (STG 4002, Multi-Channel Systems, Germany) was used to send light flashes, placed at 15 cm from the left eye of the animal, the other eye being covered with a dark cloth. It was calibrated such that the eye was illuminated with an intensity of 2 cd/cm^2 . Signals from the diamond implant were first pre-amplified with a miniature amplifier (MPA 8I, Multi-Channel Systems, Germany) via a custom adapter stacked on another adapter for 16-electrode NeuroNexus Probe and two MPA8I Amplifiers (ADPT-NN-16, Multi Channel Systems, Germany). A return electrode was positioned in the contralateral muscle of the craniotomy. Signals recorded with the 16-channel amplifier (Portable ME16-System, Multi-Channel Systems, Germany) were

digitally transmitted to a US-connected computer with a 10 kHz sampling rate. VEPs data were also analysed on Matlab following the same data processing as at EPFL3.

3. Results

A. Full-diamond implant microfabrication

The different fabrication steps described in the material and methods section (Fig. 1(A)) led to the production of full-diamond implants. The cross-section schematic on Fig. 1(B) illustrates the different layers of doped and undoped diamond in contact with the TiN conductive layer (brown). The non-doped diamond (light blue) covers all the BDD (dark blue) layer except at the electrode openings. The total thickness of these layers (intrinsic, BDD and TiN) is below 20 μm , leading to a fragile but flexible device. A silicon piece was kept at the pad extremity from the initial wafer for a better manipulation of the implant, and a 7- μm -thick parylene layer (Fig. 1(B) pink) surrounds the whole implant except around the electrodes and contact pads in order to improve the global mechanical robustness for handling purposes only. The schematic drawing in Fig. 1(C) provides a top view of the tracks which start at the contact pads and extend to the electrodes. The detached implant after laser cutting is shown on Fig. 2(A) with the contact pads above the remaining piece of wafer and the six electrodes on the other end of the implant. The BDD electrodes, surrounded by the intrinsic diamond layer, and the tracks are visible on the SEM image of the implant tail (Fig. 2(B)). The polycrystalline shape of the diamond films can be identified on Fig. 2(C), providing evidence for the appropriate growth of the diamond layers. Moreover, the picture reveals the thin and almost transparent border representing the desired insulation of the electrode by intrinsic diamond (indicated as "C*" in Fig. 2(C)).

B. Electrochemical characterization

Electrochemical characterization was performed for the three sizes of BDD electrodes (600-, 400- and 200- μm -diameter electrodes). The Bode spectrum (modulus and phase) in Fig. 3(A) spans from 1 Hz to 1 MHz (sine wave, 10 mV). The values of the impedance at 1 kHz for the 600- μm -, 400- μm - and 200- μm -diameter electrodes are respectively 7.9 k Ω , 10.3 k Ω and 48.5 k Ω , showing values much lower than results from [29]. From 1 to 10³ Hz, the impedance increases with decreasing electrode

diameter. This is consistent with the fact that larger electrode surfaces allow more easily the same flow of charge to be interfaced. From 10³ Hz to 1 MHz, the 400 μm electrode becomes less resistive than the 600 μm one, probably due to some surface roughness increasing the effective surface area on the tested samples. The linearity of the impedance modulus curve over the broad frequency range and its phase remaining around -90° indicate the capacitive behaviour of the BDD electrodes. At low frequencies (1 to 10² Hz), the 600- μm - and 400 μm -electrodes are more capacitive than the 200- μm - ones, but the 600- μm electrode shifts towards a more resistive behaviour first from 10² Hz to 5·10⁴ Hz.

The cyclic voltammograms (CV), performed at a scan rate $v = 100$ mV/s, exhibit a wide potential window of around 3 V (Fig. 3(B)) consistent with the presence of BDD on the characterised electrodes. For the three electrode diameters, the onset of the oxidation/reduction of water happens around ± 1.1 V. Additionally, the low background currents indicate that the conductive electrode is carbon-based, consistent with its boron-doped diamond nature [43]. The absence of oxidation peaks and the large width of the electrochemical potential windows (>2.8 V) suggest the absence of defects on the passivation layers. Indeed, the parylene etching step (step 10 on Fig. 1(A)) requires an energetic plasma and could create defects on the BDD electrode sites. The TiN tracks underneath, exposed to the electrolyte due to these supposed defects, could generate an electrochemical window inferior to 1.8 V [36], which is not the case here. Our electrochemical results demonstrate that the TiN tracks are well embedded inside intrinsic diamond and that the BDD electrodes are made of a continuous layer.

C. *In vivo* VEPs recording

We tested the same 600 and 400 μm electrodes during *in vivo* experiments in two different laboratories on two different rodent species.

The full-diamond custom implants were placed over the right visual cortex of the animal. The implant tail containing the BDD electrodes was layered above the dura mater to record local neural activities.

At EPFL, the mice eyes were stimulated with 20 consecutive white flashes in a Ganzfeld stimulator box at a rate of 1 Hz to evoke a cortical response. Fig. 4(A) illustrates the recorded signals after filtration and averaging for a 600- μm -diameter electrode, which show the typical positive and negative peaks of VEPs [33] with amplitudes increasing with the light intensity. Positive peaks (P1) were marked upwards and negative ones (N1) were marked downwards according to the

Fig. 3. Electrochemical characterization of 3 sizes of BDD electrode on full diamond implant – averaged values (A) EIS in PBS 0.01 M. (B) CV in LiClO₄ 0.5 M with a scan rate of 100 mV/s. The counter electrode is a platinum wire, the reference electrode is a Ag/AgCl pellet.

Fig. 4. VEPs recording on wild-type adult mice with 600- or 400- μm -diameter BDD custom electrodes. (A) VEP response to light stimulation at different intensities (1 Hz, range from 0.05 to 1 cd.s/m^2 , Ganzfeld stimulator). Mean signals ($n = 20$) are shown and errors of the mean are in light shades. VEPs traces are presented with positive peak P1 upwards according to clinical conventions [37]. Light stimulation is represented by the yellow vertical bar, (B) P1-N1 peak-to-peak amplitudes (μV) as a function of light intensity for 600 and 400- μm -diameter electrodes. (C) Latency (ms) to reach peak P1 as a function of light intensity. (D) VEPs recorded during checkerboard pattern visual stimulation (cycles/degree). Yellow and grey vertical bars correspond to the checkerboard stimulus onset. The stimulus at the grey bar is inverted compared to the yellow one. (E) P1' peak amplitude (μV) as a function of visual acuity value (cycles/degree), as mean and standard deviations, (F) Signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of recorded VEPs at different light intensities. All results are presented as mean \pm error of the mean. One-way ANOVA with Dunn-Sidak multiple-comparison test: ns = non-significant, $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, $***p < 0.001$. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

International Society for Clinical Electrophysiology of Vision (ISCEV) standards [37]. P1-N1 peak-to-peak average amplitudes measured for the 600- μm -diameter electrode increased respectively from 144.1 ± 9.0 , 145.9 ± 6.8 , $222.0 \pm 12.6 \mu\text{V}$, to $233.7 \pm 19.6 \mu\text{V}$ for light intensities varying from 0.05, 0.1, 0.5 and 1 cd.s/m^2 (Fig. 4(B)). A similar increase in response amplitudes when increasing the light intensities were observed for both 600- μm - and 400- μm -diameter BDD electrodes. Such increase showed statistically significant differences (Fig. 4(B)) for the 600- μm electrode when light intensity increased from 0.1 to 0.5 cd.s/m^2 ($***p = 0.00049$), and for the 400- μm electrode when light intensity was raised from 0.5 to 1 cd.s/m^2 ($*p = 0.035$). The amplitudes of the signals recorded with the 600- μm electrode were also higher than the ones recorded with the 400- μm one. Fig. 4(C) displays time latencies defined as the time to reach the first peak P1. One-way ANOVA and pairwise comparison demonstrate no significant differences between all intensities and between all intensity pairs.

Fig. 4(D) shows cortical recordings using a 600- μm -diameter electrode upon a black and white alternating chessboard of pattern visual stimulation at 1 Hz, which is a classic test to assess visual acuity [37]. In this test, visual evoked potentials become flat when the size of

alternating white and black squares matrix or when the number of cycles/degree are no longer detectable by the visual cortex. Fig. 4(D, E) elicit clear visual evoked potentials with similar amplitudes at 0.1 or 0.2 cycles/degree ($62.11 \pm 5.62 \mu\text{V}$ and $72.15 \pm 7.44 \mu\text{V}$ respectively). By contrast, the mean peak amplitude is reduced to $46.34 \pm 7.05 \mu\text{V}$ at 0.3 cycles/degree, which generated a statistically significant difference than the measurement at 0.2 cycles/degree ($*p = 0.025$ at a 5% alpha level). These signals recorded with our full-diamond implant indicate a visual function threshold between 0.2 and 0.3 cycles/degree for wild-type mice slightly below previous study indicating a value of 0.5 cycles/degree for C57BU6 [40] or C57BL/6 J mice [47]. Our difference could result from the greater distance of the eye to the checkerboard screen in our study (50 cm versus 16 cm in [46]), from some eye misalignment and also from the progressive eye cloudiness due to the anesthetic state in our experiment.

Finally, the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) was calculated for the VEPs recorded with the 600- μm - and 400- μm -diameter electrodes at different light intensities (Fig. 4(F)). The signal quality is generally speaking higher for the largest electrode diameter, and higher at the highest light intensity used (1 cd.s/m^2), reaching 7.7 ± 1.5 .

Additionally, at IDV, we used a collimated white LED controlled by a stimulus generator to send light flashes to the left eye of the rat. The average amplitude of P1 recorded was around 100 μV (Fig. 5). The presence of a second positive peak (P2) shortly after the first one (P1) resembles the overall shape of VEPs described in literature.

Through these two sets of experiments, we demonstrated the successful recording of VEPs using the fabricated full-diamond implants.

4. Discussion

It is the first time, to our knowledge, that such a manufacturing process was developed. We demonstrated a successful release of full-a flexible diamond neural implant with BDD electrodes and intrinsic diamond passivation, embedded in an ultra-thin film technology (below 20 μm) compatible with standard micro-manufacturing.

Most neural flexible implants for brain-machine interfaces are made of biocompatible polymers with various electrode materials (metals, semiconductors, organic polymers). Lately, interest has grown for carbon-based materials because of their high stability and biocompatibility but also their promising electro-chemical properties for neural interfacing applications [[6,14,26]. BDD material has been previously applied on such polymer implants to generate biocompatible electrodes and to record neurons *in vitro* when deposited on rigid substrates [15,38]. In parallel, intrinsic diamond was used to fabricate biocompatible and hermetic cases [18,35]. Here we combined these results and developed a new process to fabricate neural implants with BDD electrodes and TiN tracks embedded in intrinsic diamond layers using localised growth of intrinsic diamond in a cleanroom environment. For this, we make use of the masking properties of Aluminium nitride (AlN) for localised growth inside the diamond reactor. Indeed AlN appears resilient to the high CVD diamond plasma conditions allowing the well-defined shape of the electrodes (Fig. 2(B) and (C)).

The intrinsic diamond encapsulating the conductive layers and the presence of BDD electrodes offer a strong protection against biological reactions that can occur post-implantation [25]. The high stability of diamond precludes water penetration and consequent delamination. The choice of TiN material to define the conductive tracks was motivated by its natural ability to withstand diamond growth conditions and a reliable adhesion surface for diamond. Long-lasting ageing experiments are on-going to confirm the absence of delamination of such diamond implants and their ability to endure harsh biological

Fig. 5. VEPs recording on Long Evans rats with 400- μm -diameter BDD custom electrodes. Mean signals averaged over 100 repetitions and standard deviations (light blue shades) in response to light stimulation (first column) and to hidden light stimulation (second column). Red line indicates the trigger from the light stimulus. VEPs traces are presented with positive peaks (P1, P2, P3) upwards. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

environments. The fabricated flexible device also had to be slightly rigidified for better manipulation during surgery by parylene encapsulation, a class IV material that can be legally used for clinical applications [31,49]. Here the role of the parylene is just to mimic the role that will play an alternative biodegradable polymer to be used to help handling the ultrathin and flexible diamond implant during the surgery step. We are currently working on such biodegradable polymers which role will be to provide rigidity for handling, while after being dissolved a few weeks after surgery will enable the diamond ECoG implant to fully adopt its high flexibility for better contact with the contours of the cortex. Here the Parylene is only use as a mimic of this future biodegradable polymer. A remaining silicon piece facilitates handling and connection for animal experimentations. Overall it seems that the device could easily comply with legal standards for future clinical translations.

The 3 V-wide potential window in the CV measurement demonstrates that our electrodes are clearly made of BDD. Although the electrochemical window of our BDD electrodes is lower than the 4 V window of the 3-mm-diameter N-UNCD electrodes described in literature [19], it is still twice wider compared to classical metals such as platinum (1.3 V, [10]), or novel materials such as Poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene)-poly(styrenesulfonate) (PEDOT-PSS) coated electrodes (1.7 V in 0.9 % NaCl, [48]) or sputtered iridium oxide films (SIROFs) electrodes (1.4 V in PBS, [11]).

The hypothesis of a rough BDD electrode surface is further supported by the low impedance values measured at 1 kHz along with the satisfactory conductivity of the fabricated TiN. Compared to the previously mentioned materials, the impedance of our BDD electrodes is in the same order of magnitude as 200- μm -diameter SIROFs electrodes [11].

This first technological success in terms of BDD-electrode-based implant fabrication validates the future production of a next generation device with far more electrodes per device, enabling better statistics and recording performances over a larger total surface. The thinness of the device allows its flexibility and the intrinsic diamond coating contributes to its longevity, hence the suitability of such device for neural stimulation purposes.

For brain-machine interfaces, signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is a *sine qua non* condition for quality restitution of neural signals. Although the electrodes here have a relatively large diameter compared to standard BCIs ($\approx 30 \mu\text{m}$), they are nonetheless suitable for neural recording on the brain surface considering that the diameter of current micro ECoG implants can reach up to 1 mm diameter.

The flash VEPs recorded here demonstrate the functionality of the full-diamond implant and its BDD electrodes in a recording mode, as it was performed with two different experimental setups on rodents (Long Evans rats and C57BL mice). In both cases, the presence of a large second positive peak after the first positive P1 and negative N1 ones resembles the overall shape of VEPs described in literature [53]. In another study from [7] where VEPs were recorded on rabbits with printed platinum electrodes, mean amplitudes at 1 cd.s/m^2 were reported to be around 300 μV . Such differences with our measured values in amplitudes could be imputed to animal species differences and placement of the electrode on the brain. The SNR was measured to be similar to $50 \times 50 \mu\text{m}^2$ gold electrodes used for spiking activity recordings even though doped graphene ones were 6 times higher [32]. And larger electrodes correspond to lower SNR as usual, which is our case with 400 μm diameter. In addition, we must remember that edge effects highly contribute to the bio-electronic capacitive value and therefore to the impedance decrease leading the noise reduction.

Diamond was already shown to be highly biocompatible both *ex vivo* and *in vivo* [52]. In addition, the low impedance value of the fabricated full diamond implants is unprecedented for diamond-based electrodes. These *in vivo* results constitute the first step towards the micro-fabrication of a denser full-diamond electrodes array which could serve clinically as a chronic neuro-prosthesis. Complementary works are under process to certify the stability and hermeticity of the full-diamond structure through ageing experiments. Future studies will have to

explore how to generate smaller electrodes with a higher developed surface. However, we here provide the first proof of concept that our manufactured thin film full-diamond-based implant can be used for neural recording. More technological developments will be required to obtain a full-diamond implant for bi-directional stimulation-recording abilities.

5. Conclusions

In summary, we designed, fabricated a novel flexible thin film full-diamond implant for neural recording, and we validated their functionality as ECoG arrays through *in vivo* experiments.

We reported the methods for manufacturing and characterising these implants. Diamond was mainly selected for its biocompatibility and inertness leading to little tissue reaction and long-term capabilities. These thin implants composed of BDD electrodes in contact with neural tissues are also embedded into intrinsic diamond and seem resistant enough to external mechanical forces as a result of the remarkable properties of diamond.

These characteristics promote the long-term stability of such novel BCI. Besides these results, electrodes were tested in multiple animal facilities under different conditions, and each time VEPs were recorded at the surface of the cortex of rodents, proving that the new implants are capable of recording cortical signals. Both the *ex vivo* characterization and the successful *in vivo* recordings confirm the suitable use of diamond as a material of choice for neuronal recordings, opening new pathways in the ECoG field towards long-lasting chronic electrodes.

In the future, we will work towards smaller electrodes with 3D texturing allowing very low noise levels and covering a larger surface of the visual cortex. Therefore, this study serves as a proof-of-concept for further design of a 32-channel whole-diamond ECoG.

Funding

“This work has been funded by the European Research Council (ERC) established by the European Commission. Lionel Rousseau has received support of an ERC starting grant 2017 (758700 — NEURODIAM). This project also received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 - Research and Innovation Framework Programme program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 861423 (enTRAIN Vision). Additionally, we acknowledge the support of LabEx LIFESENSES (ANR-10-LABX-65) and IHU FORESIGHT (ANR-18-IAHU-01).”

Institutional review board statement

“The animal study protocol was approved by the following Institutional Review Boards: 1. according to the animal authorisation GE/193/19 approved by the Département de l'emploi, des affaires sociales et de la santé (DEAS), Direction générale de la santé de la République et Canton de Genève, 2. approved by the Local Animal Ethics Committee No 005 (registration number APAFIS #15258-2018052811521506 v1), for the Institute of Vision, Paris, France.

Informed consent statement

“Not applicable.”

Prime novelty

The first demonstration of the technological fabrication of full diamond implants composed of boron doped diamond electrochemical electrodes connected and embedded in watertight intrinsic diamond providing high mechanical flexibility. Tests validated on rodents exposed to optical light stimulation enabled to probe visual evoked potentials directly on their visual cortex.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

F.C. Wilfinger: Methodology. **J.M. Zhang:** Methodology. **D. Nguyen:** Methodology. **J. Dégardin:** Methodology. **P. Bergonzo:** Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **S. Picaud:** Conceptualization, Supervision. **E. Borda:** Methodology. **D. Ghezzi:** Investigation, Methodology, Supervision. **E. Scorsone:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **G. Lissorgues:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **L. Rousseau:** Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

“The authors declare no conflict of interest, and declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.”

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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